

Quantitative structure activity relationship studies on a series of 1,3-diaryl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-2H-isoindole derivatives as potent and selective Cox-2 inhibitors

A. K. Srivastava*, Archana and Meetu Jaiswal

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : qsarlab_am@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 7 November 2006, accepted 10 January 2007

Abstract : The quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) of analogues of diaryl tetrahydroisoindole focusing on the modification of the ring fused to pyrrole nucleus, is discussed. The anti-inflammatory activity of these compounds is found to be dominantly controlled by electronic and steric factors, X_{eq} and ${}^1\chi^V$ in combination with indicator parameters.

Keywords : Cyclooxygenase, QSAR; quantitative structure activity relationship.

QSAR is a major factor in contemporary drug designing. The molecular descriptors like geometric, electronic, hydrophobic and steric parameters and their combinations have widely been employed in QSAR studies, with a view to provide better rational design of some more potent drugs in the present series.

In the present QSAR studies, IC_{50} values were converted to pIC_{50} based upon the equation

$$pIC_{50} = -\log IC_{50}$$

In the present QSAR studies molecular descriptors are calculated using the information given as below :

Molecular descriptors	Formula	Basis	Ref.
Molecular connectivity	${}^1\chi^V = \sum \left[\delta_i \delta_j \right]^{-0.5}$	Valence delta values	1
Equalized electronegativity	$X_{eq} = \frac{N}{\sum (\nu / x)}$	Electronegativity of atoms	2
Partition coefficient	$\log P = \sum_n a_n f_n + \sum_m b_m F_m$	Hydrophobicity of molecules	3

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are widely used to treat pain fever and osteoarthritis. Recently it has been postulated that Cox-2 inhibitors may effectively relieve in symptoms of osteoarthritis.

IL-1-stimulated chondrocytes from normal cartilage

expressed the Cox-2 gene and produced the Cox-2 protein followed by PGE_2 release⁴. The PGE_2 over induced in osteoarthritic cartilage has been shown to coincide with Cox-2 impregnation hence suggesting that PGE_2 may be differentially regulated in normal and osteoarthritic cartilage⁵. The structures of the compounds related to the cyclopentenyl lactones after optimization Celecoxib and Rofecoxib was developed⁶. After several modifications in structure in order to enhance the Cox-2 inhibition potency a leading compound (1) had been reported. QSAR studies have been discussed on analogues of diaryl tetrahydroisoindole focusing on the modifications of the ring fused to the pyrrole nucleus.

Results and discussion

All compounds of this series with calculated physico-chemical parameters and their biological activities are given in Table 1. Before studying the correlation, we checked the correlation matrix of the parameters (Table 2). The regression analysis of the data presented in Table 1 gave the following equations.

$$pIC_{50} = -0.540 (\pm 0.356) {}^1\chi^V + 12.959 \quad (1)$$

$$n = 11, R = 0.753, R^2 = 0.567, R^2_A = 0.519,$$

$$F_{(1,9)} = 11.825, S.E. = 0.618, Q = 1.218$$

where n is the number of data points; R is the correlation coefficient; R^2 is the coefficient of determination; S.E. is the standard error of estimation; F is the variance ratio between the calculated and observed activities; figures within the parenthesis are confidence intervals at 95% level; R^2_A is also known as explained variance (E.V.) which when multiplied by 100 gives the percentage of the variance in activity that can be accounted for by the equation and Q is the quality factor⁷, defined as the ratio

of the correlation coefficient R to the standard error of estimation (S.E.) [$Q = R/S.E.$]

Eq. (1) shows significant correlation between ${}^1\chi^V$ and activity. It accounts for 51.9% explained variance.

From correlation matrix (Table 2) ${}^1\chi^V$ has no autocorrelation and therefore can be used with other parameters. The following regression equations were resulted.

$$pIC_{50} = -0.557 (\pm 0.393) {}^1\chi^V + 2.346 (\pm 13.762) X_{eq} + 7.628 \quad (2)$$

$$n = 11, R = 0.758, R^2 = 0.567, R^2_A = 0.576,$$

$$F_{(2,8)} = 5.434, S.E. = 0.650, Q = 1.166$$

Table 1. Biological activities and physico-chemical data for various isoindole derivatives as Cox-2 inhibitors

Sl. no.	Ring	R	R_1	R_2	X_{eq}	${}^1\chi^V$	$\log P$	I_1	I_2	I_3	$\log (1/IC_{50})$			
											Obsd. (pIC ₅₀)	Calcd. eq. (4)	Calcd. eq. (5)	Calcd. eq. (6)
1.		H	H	H	2.2901	8.5830	5.87	0	0	0	8.5086	8.7872	8.1355	8.3239
2.		H	H	H	2.2996	8.2355	4.95	0	0	0	7.8386	8.4627	8.3345	8.4125
3.		H	H	H	2.3083	6.7034	4.24	0	0	0	9.1549	8.1650	9.2116	8.4808
4.		H	F	F	2.3754	7.4778	1.02	1	0	0	8.5376	8.5663	8.7682	8.7908
5.		H	H	H	2.3058	8.2817	4.74	0	0	0	8.5850	8.2510	8.3080	8.4327
6.		H	F	F	2.3660	8.5995	1.610	1	0	0	8.9586	8.8874	8.1261	8.7340
7.		H	F	F	2.3815	8.3143	0.92	1	0	0	8.3467	8.3579	8.2894	8.8005
8.		H	CH ₃ SO ₂	F	2.3643 3	11.789	2.83	0	0	1	6.1549	6.2527	6.2999	6.1549
9.		H	H	H	2.2996	8.6621	5.40	0	1	0	8.7958	8.4627	9.100	8.3692
10.		H	F	F	2.3553	8.9810	2.15	1	1	0	9.2218	9.2529	8.9175	8.6820
11.		H	H	H	2.3101	8.7152	5.40	0	0	0	7.4485	8.1041	8.0598	8.3692

Table 2. Correlation matrix among the parameters used for isoindole derivatives as Cox-2 inhibitors

	${}^1\chi^V$	$\log P$	X_{eq}
${}^1\chi^V$	1.00	-0.097	0.249
$\log P$		1.00	0.971
X_{eq}			1.00

$$pIC_{50} = -0.545 (\pm 0.377) {}^1\chi^V - 0.063 (\pm 0.249) \log P + 13.225 \quad (3)$$

$$n = 11, R = 0.765, R^2 = 0.585, R^2_A = 0.482,$$

$$F_{(2,8)} = 5.658, S.E. = 0.642, Q = 1.191$$

The both correlation eqs. (2), (3) have their F ratio val-

ues significant at 95% level [$F_{(2,8)} = 4.46$].

Indicator variables⁸ parameters are some time used in linear, multiple regression analysis account for certain features which cannot be described by continuous variables. In QSAR equations they normally describe a certain structural element, be it a substituent or another molecular fragment. So in order to study their role different parameters with different indicators gave the following equations.

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -34.158 (\pm 18.828) X_{\text{eq}} + 2.692 (\pm 1.328) I_1 + 87.013 \quad (4)$$

$$n = 11, R = 0.857, R^2 = 0.734, R^2_A = 0.668,$$

$$F_{(2,8)} = 11.088, \text{S.E.} = 0.514, Q = 1.667$$

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.572 (\pm 0.279) {}^1\chi^V + 1.009 (\pm 0.858) I_2 + 13.049 \quad (5)$$

$$n = 11, R = 0.880, R^2 = 0.775, R^2_A = 0.718,$$

$$F_{(2,8)} = 13.781, \text{S.E.} = 0.473, Q = 1.860$$

$$\text{pIC}_{50} = -0.096 (\pm 0.217) \log P - 2.461 (\pm 1.359) I_3 + 8.889 \quad (6)$$

$$n = 11, R = 0.829, R^2 = 0.688, R^2_A = 0.611,$$

$$F_{(2,8)} = 8.853, \text{S.E.} = 0.557, Q = 1.488$$

I_1 indicator is used for F at R^2 position of phenyl ring, I_2 indicator is used for ring at position R on pyrrole nucleus and I_3 is for $-\text{CH}_3\text{SO}_2$ at R_2 position.

In eqs. (4), (6) explained variance is 66.8% and 66.1% eq. (5) accounts for the best regression equation. The value of regression coefficient is high and S.E. gets lowered. Explained variance is 71.8%. The F value is significant at 95% level [$F_{(2,8)} = 4.46$].

An overview presented by the equations reveal that in future designing of this class of drug with reference to their activity IC_{50} , the following points may be kept in mind.

(i) In eq. (4) the sign of coefficient of parameter and indicator clears that less electronegative groups are preferred, as fluorine F is the only electronegative element present in the series so F should be retained at R^2 position of phenyl ring.

(ii) The sign of coefficient of parameter ${}^1\chi^V$ (-)ve and indicator is (+)ve in eq. (5) indicates that small bridged

substituents should be taken.

(iii) In eq. (6) both parameter and indicator have (-)ve sign of coefficient means CH_3SO_2 group is strictly avoided at phenyl ring, the substituents should be less hydrophobic in nature.

These findings are in conformity with earlier findings⁹ where they have also stated that six membered ring fused to the non N -substituted pyrrole nucleus appears to be of prime importance for obtaining significant results, while a 5-membered ring containing derivatives seems to produce inconsistent results a one or two carbon bridge added to the six membered ring (compd. 9) improves activity, specially when a difluoro substitution is present on the phenyl rings appended to the pyrrole nucleus giving the most potent PGE_2 inhibitor (compd. 10).

Another alternative for obtaining the most suitable model is to estimate pIC_{50} for eq. (5) and compare it with its observed values given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by grant (1648)/100/EMR II awarded by CSIR, New Delhi.

References

1. E. J. Kupchik, *Quant. Struct. Act. Relat.*, 1985, 4, 123; 1986, 5, 95; 1988, 7, 57.
2. R. T. Sanderson, *J. Chem. Edu.*, 1952, 29, 539.
3. G. C. Nys and R. F. Rekker, *Chem. Therap.*, 1973, 8, 521.
4. M. J. Parnham, *Inflamm. Res.*, 1998, 47, 43.
5. C. C. Chan, I. A. Dibattista, J. Zhao, J. P. Pelletier, J. Martel Pelletier, B. P. Kenngdy, C. Brideau and I. W. Rodger, International Association of Inflammation Society, Brighton, Sept. 17, 1995.
6. J. Wallace, B. Chin and Celecoxib, *Curr. Opin. Central Peripheral Neuro. Syst.*, 1999, 1, 132; C. Black, E. Grimm, S. Leger, P. Prasit and Z. Wang, World Patent Wo 9619469, 1995; F. Kamali and Rofecoxib, *Curr. Opin. Central Peripheral*, 1999, 126.
7. L. Pogliani, *Amino Acids*, 1994, 6, 141.
8. A. T. Balaban, I. Motoc, D. Bonchev and O. Mekenyam, "Steric Effects in Drug Design", eds. M. Charton and I. Motoc, Akademik-Verlag, Berlin, 1983; S. Chatterjee, A. Hodi and B. Price, "Regression Analysis by Examples", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 2000.
9. Bernard Portevin, Charles Tordjman, Philippe Pastoureaux *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, 43, 4582.